

Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communications (DEC) Plan

Work Package: 7

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Table of Contents

Document Revision History.....	4
Executive Summary.....	5
1. Introduction.....	6
2. Main Objectives.....	6
3. SEA-Quester Flagship Outputs	7
4. Strategy	8
4.1 Target Audiences.....	8
4.1.1 EU and UN Policymakers	9
4.1.2 National and Local Government officials and managing authorities	9
4.1.3 Members of the Scientific Community.....	10
4.1.4 European Civil Society and Arctic communities	11
4.2 Communication Strategies.....	11
4.2.1 Social Media	12
4.2.2 Media Outreach	12
4.3 Dissemination Strategies.....	13
4.3.1 Polar Clustering	13
4.3.2 Dissemination Events	14
4.4 Exploitation Strategies	14
4.4.1 Exploitation of Data.....	15
4.4.2 Exploitation of New Knowledge	15
4.4.3 Risks and barriers to exploitation and their mitigation	15
Table 1 Mitigation strategy for risks and barriers to exploitation of SEA-Quester results	16
5. DEC Tools.....	16
5.1 Tools for internal communication.....	17
5.1.1 ECR Mentoring	17
5.1.2 Intranet.....	17
5.1.3 Project Gatherings and Meetings.....	17
5.1.4 Nested Storylines	18
5.1.5 “Mini-Guides”	18
5.2 Tools for external communication and dissemination.....	18
5.2.1 Open Access Journal Articles and Scientific Databases.....	19
5.2.2 Website	19
5.2.3 Newsletter.....	19
5.2.4 Promotional Materials.....	20

5.2.5 Podcast Series	20
5.2.6 EU Commission Tools	20
5.3 Social Media	20
5.4 Media Outreach	22
6. Action Plan	22
<i>Table 2. Communication Action Plan.....</i>	<i>27</i>
7. Inventories and Networks	27
7.1 Inventory of Relevant Projects, Organizations, and Associations	27
7.3 Target Media Networks.....	28
7.4 Social Media Channels	29
Table 3. Social media accounts of consortium members.....	33
8. Impact Monitoring and Reporting.....	34
<i>Table 4. SEA-Quester Key Impact Indicators and responsibilities for monitoring them</i>	<i>36</i>
8. Annex – Practical guides	36
SEA-Quester contact/ mailing list	47
SEA-Quester impact survey	50
SEA-Quester branding guide	51
SEA-Quester storyline guidance	62

Document Revision History

Author(s)	Date	Change Records	Revision Issue
Paige Eikeland	07-31-2024	-Added Revision History Table -Added PLANT Project to Table 3 and list of relevant EU Projects in Section 7	1.0
Artur Palacz	18-02-2026	Added updated link to data management plan; updated EOV recommendations; updated Channels and Outputs for National and Local Government officials; updated details on polar clustering;	2.0
Sabrina Heerema, Paige Eikeland	03-03-2026	Added a few words about using monthly meetings to flag or capture news for promotion; replaced media packages with media contact page to avoid misunderstanding, added a sentence each to the sections on POMP and ECRs regarding monthly coordination meetings. Removed the page of listed Annexes, these are meant to be internal guidance documents only. Added details of collaboration with POMP.	2.1

Executive Summary

From project start to end, the SEA-Quester project hopes to meaningfully engage with stakeholders, attract young experts to our team, raise awareness of how public money is spent, and to showcase the success of European collaboration. This plan jointly presents guidelines for SEA-Quester partners to follow in disseminating, exploiting, and communicating project activities and results, as these actions are highly interdependent.

The goals of the SEA-Quester Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication (DEC) Plan are to:

- contribute to the international scientific body of knowledge and assessments of Polar Blue Carbon potential and have these results inform science-based decisions and policy (specifically targeting Nationally Determined Contribution estimates)
- facilitate dialogue between National and European governmental bodies, European citizens, and NGOs regarding Polar Blue Carbon
- optimize biodiversity monitoring and ecosystem services valuation in emerging polar environments through project outputs

The SEA-Quester consortium consists of 12 partner institutions who will each contribute to achieving these collective goals. However, this document is intended as a user guide on how partners can work together to strategically communicate about these activities and outputs in a coordinated and professional way to stakeholders and target audiences. The communication strategy tackles how to describe and discuss project activities and results to multiple audiences through clear messages and use of the right media channels. SEA-Quester's four (4) main target audiences are: 1) the scientific community, 2) European national governments, 3) international policymakers, and 4) European citizens. Secondary audiences include industry (including authorities or SMEs), local governments, and civil society organizations/NGOs.

Dissemination facilitates the free and open access to, and promotion of knowledge and results generated from project activities. The primary project output will be published articles in peer-reviewed scientific journals, contributions to scientific or targeted conferences, and in databases. This allows the project to maximise the impact of results, allow other researchers to progress further, contribute to the advancement of state-of-the-art science and technology, and make scientific results a common good. Relevant results should also be made accessible to our other main target audiences through more tailored products such as podcasts, videos, and exhibitions.

Exploitation makes concrete use of the disseminated results for commercial, societal, or political purposes. The knowledge generated and shared from the project can have a positive impact on societal actors working towards transformational change, such as by contributing to the creation of roadmaps, prototypes, software, and by sharing knowledge, skills, and data – especially towards the end of the project and beyond. This can benefit innovation and support the economy and European society to help tackle the triple planetary crisis of climate change, biodiversity loss, and pollution/waste. In this way, SEA-Quester can respond to the demand for solutions to mitigate the climate crisis while evaluating other environmental and societal impacts.

After a brief introduction, Section 3 describes flagship products – primary project outputs beyond scientific journal articles. Sections 4 and 5 provide more information about strategies and information about main target audiences, communication tools, and establishes a project visual identity with

suggested storylines. Section 6 provides a concrete action plan and Section 7 assigns responsibilities for communication and dissemination activities targeting all 4 main audiences. The impact of the project's dissemination, exploitation, and communication activities will be evaluated by the European Commission using both quantitative and qualitative impact measures. These key impact indicators (KIIs) are described in further detail in Section 8.

1. Introduction

The SEA-Quester project, Grant #101136480, aims to tackle uncertainties about the future of carbon sequestration in polar regions and conduct both fundamental and applied research into Blue Carbon production, export, and sequestration given the emergence of novel ecosystems.

To reach this goal, strategic communication and dissemination of research activities and results is essential, and this plan serves as an overview for stakeholder interactions, both passive and active, to be used in tandem with the project data management plan (most recent version available at: <https://zenodo.org/records/18660769>). These are closely linked: this communication strategy outlines HOW and WHAT we will tell specific groups about the project; the dissemination strategy BUILDS on communication with RESULTS; and the data management plan outlines how results will be responsibly stored and maintained to be USED in the future – creating lasting impact beyond the scope of the project, a key component of the exploitation strategy. The internal project communications platform (D9.2) is also integral to managing data, co-creating outputs, scheduling, and managing internal project-related matters.

This document presents the next iteration of the of the DEC Plan which is intended to be a living document. Updating and revising the strategy as needed reflects the changing priorities of the projects as stakeholder needs become known in more detail and their feedback is received.

2. Main Objectives

The primary dissemination, exploitation, and communication objectives for the SEA-Quester project are fourfold:

1. Support local and national governments or managing authorities on decisions regarding fisheries policy, marine spatial planning, and Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs).
2. Support European Union and United Nations-level policymakers on decisions regarding the Arctic and Antarctic strategy, biodiversity strategy, and the EU Green Deal.
3. Support the scientific community by addressing knowledge gaps on carbon sequestration and human activities in emerging polar and sub-polar ecosystems.
4. Promote ocean literacy with a focus on marine biogeochemical cycles and Blue Carbon outside of tropical coastal ecosystems (elevate “Polar Blue Carbon” in global discussions).

Results from SEA-Quester include scientific publications and presentations, open-access data and models, participation in selected working and assessment groups, policy briefs, factsheets, and other flagship products (see Section 3 below). Results and outputs are intended to be utilised by EU and UN policymakers, national and local governments, the scientific community, European civil society, and Arctic communities, and will be created with these target groups in mind.

3. SEA-Quester Flagship Outputs

In addition to peer-reviewed scientific publications, SEA-Quester will develop other types of outputs to communicate with target audiences, disseminate results, and utilise new project knowledge in future efforts. These “flagship” outputs for the project are reprinted from the accepted project proposal here, with supporting deliverables listed in italics below.

- 1. Blue Carbon accounting template:** lay the foundations for a fit-for-purpose blue carbon accounting scheme with balance sheets not just for carbon sequestration, but other impacted marine ecosystem services such as fisheries production, accounting for residence times and couched in terms of net fluxes and allowing for a better estimation of the potential of European and polar seas to take up and store carbon now and in future.
Supporting SEA-Quester Deliverables: D4.2 -transient time of carbon sequestration, D5.1 -Carbon residence time, D5.2 -long-term sequestration, D6.1 -Climate change effects on carbon solubility and inorganic carbon reservoirs
Supporting POMP Deliverables: D3.1 -polar open ocean ecosystem CO₂ mitigation potential and vulnerability to and feedbacks with climate change, D3.2 -coastal and fjord ecosystem CO₂ mitigation potential and patterns of change
- 2. Biomass-Sequestration Amplification Factor (BSAF):** the ratio of carbon sequestration processes supported to total biomass carrying out those processes, a useful metric when considering trade-offs between biomass harvesting through fisheries vs carbon sequestration ecosystem services, and allowing comparisons between species
- 3. Blue Carbon sequestration potential maps:** Maps of potential carbon sequestration in current and emerging polar and sub-polar ecosystems provided to facilitate simple spatial overlay analysis on current and planned marine protected areas, maps of ongoing human and industrial activities, and weighing of the effects of protection vs. no protection on carbon sequestration ecosystem services
Supporting SEA-Quester Deliverables: M8.1 -First GIS data layers integrated onto project website, D1.4 -Emerging intertidal seaweed ecosystems in the European Arctic, D6.3 -effects on global blue carbon
Supporting POMP Deliverables: D2.3 -Benthic biodiversity and hotspots of carbon storage and sequestration, D4.3 -report on prioritized areas for conservation to mitigate loss of polar C- and biodiversity rich habitats
- 4. NDC Blueprint:** pave the way for accounting emerging novel ecosystems as Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). SEA-Quester will provide a feasibility assessment, combining scientific results and stakeholder interviews, and support national policies and management by providing a decision-making tool for blue carbon (e.g., “sea-forestation”) vs. conservation or other activities such as tourism.
Supporting SEA-Quester Deliverables: D7.1 -Policy Assessment; D8.4 -Recommendations for Blue Carbon Accounting Policy Brief
Supporting POMP Deliverables: D4.4 -policy paper with recommendations for MPA/conservation assessment guidelines addressing C-rich habitats, M5.8 -policy brief

5. **Multiple stressor assessment:** Quantification of the effects of multiple human activities on blue carbon, allowing for its inclusion in integrated ecosystem management.
Supporting SEA-Quester Deliverables: D6.2 -Effects of multiple stressors on carbon stocks and sequestration

6. **EOV recommendations:** develop observations and monitoring of Blue Carbon within the framework of Essential Ocean Variables (EOVs) and regional EV frameworks by providing recommendations for revised observing requirements and ocean indicators, as well as data, ground-truthing, improved regional algorithms, and recommendations for the next generation of earth observations. The recommendations are developed in partnership with the BioEcoOcean project which explicitly develops EOVs for Biology and Ecosystems.
Supporting SEA-Quester Milestones: M7.2 -IOCCG representative on GOOS BGC/IOCCP

7. **Multimedia Exhibit:** An interactive exhibit including photos and videos to creatively display many of the concepts presented on the website, including the “what,” “why,” and “where” of Polar Blue Carbon, the knowledge gaps and main discoveries, threats from climate change and other human activities, and policy recommendations.
Supporting SEA-Quester Deliverables: D8.2 -Mid-term policy event, EU Polar Cluster policy and outreach events or Arctic Circle Assembly

8. **Podcast:** a professional podcast series on Polar Blue Carbon to bring the voices of researchers and policy experts to our target audiences in a new way. The style of the podcast will be moderated discussions between two experts, or the host talking with one expert to tell a polar blue carbon related story of interest.
Supporting SEA-Quester Deliverables: D8.4 – Project Website

9. **Animator Explainer Website:** an innovative, animated “explainer” website on polar blue carbon will be updated throughout the project. As the project progresses, additional pages and links will be added to the main dynamic storyline, allowing viewers to either stick to the basics, or click to go more in-depth and learn more. www.polarbluecarbon.eu or www.sea-quester.eu, with a link to the internal communication platform (NextCloud).
Supporting SEA-Quester Deliverables: D8.4 – Project Website, D9.2 -Communication platform and procedures

10. **ECR Mentoring:** targeted, one-on-one support to PhD students and post-docs wishing to expand their skillset in creating outputs targeted to non-technical or non-scientific audiences. Mentees will define goals and then receive feedback, resources, skill workshops, and expert evaluations from GRID-Arendal staff.

4. Strategy

4.1 Target Audiences

SEA-Quester has 4 target audience groups. Their relevance to the project, specific objectives in communicating with them, the type of messaging we will use, channels, and project outputs targeting these groups are outlined in this section. Section 6 (Action Plan) covers more specific activities. To the

extent possible, we will jointly disseminate project results and coordinate communications to these audiences together with our sister project POMP (Polar Ocean Mitigation Potential).

4.1.1 EU and UN Policymakers

Individuals and groups who contribute to implementation of the European Green Deal, UNFCCC Ocean and Climate Change Dialogue, Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF), and EU Arctic, Antarctic, Biodiversity Strategies and work to achieve the following:

- increased protection of the marine environment;
- sustainable fisheries (particularly in mesopelagic), including regional fisheries management organizations (RFMOs);
- protection of vulnerable areas in the Arctic and Antarctic;
- implementation of the European Green Deal's biodiversity and climate objectives;
- supporting the implementation of the Kunming Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, in particular targets 2 (Restore 30% of all Degraded Ecosystems), 3 (Conserve 30% of Land, Waters and Seas), 8 (Minimize the Impacts of Climate Change on Biodiversity and Build Resilience), and 11 (Restore, Maintain, and Enhance Nature's Contributions to People)
- strengthening the ocean – climate – biodiversity nexus;
- climate-neutrality by maintaining and enhancing natural carbon sinks and stocks in marine and polar ecosystems, while preserving and enhancing their biodiversity;
- the inclusion of carbon- and biodiversity-rich marine habitats and accounting in nationally determined contributions (NDCs) and associated national climate plans and strategies (NAPs), or National Biodiversity Strategies and Action Plans (NBSAPs);
- Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) on Climate Action (13) and Life Below Water (14).

Objectives for EU and UN Policymakers

To increase their understanding of the trade-offs between biomass harvest and carbon sequestration; their knowledge concerning the interplay between biodiversity, carbon sequestration, and economic development in emerging novel ecosystems; and elevate polar blue carbon as a topic in the general international climate discourse.

Channels and Outputs for EU and UN Policymakers

Communication with this audience group is planned primarily via political or policy events (such as Arctic Circle and M8.2 -joint mid-term policy event), through presentations or policy briefs as conversation starters, and also includes traveling exhibit or display, interactive knowledge and data products that build off of the primary scientific output (peer-reviewed journal articles) flagship outputs (such as a blue carbon accounting template), and a policy assessment on the viability of inclusion of blue carbon within NDCs, fisheries management, and other related policies (D7.3).

4.1.2 National and Local Government officials and managing authorities

Individuals or departments who determine fisheries policy or set quotas, coordinate marine spatial planning, or implement ecosystem-based management (EbM) approaches, or are responsible for calculating, reporting, or auditing NDCs.

Objectives for National and Local Government officials

Our specific objectives are to increase their understanding of the mitigation potential for polar blue carbon (or lack thereof) and implications for management in areas under their jurisdiction, to provide marine spatial planning data that meaningfully captures some measure of carbon sequestration and increase their understanding of the relative contribution of different organisms to carbon sequestration (such as through the Biological-Sequestration Amplification Factor, or BSAF, of different commercial and non-commercial species).

Channels and Outputs for National and Local Government officials

We will communicate to this group through attendance at relevant events, but also through a workshop on Svalbard (M8.3) and other initiatives in collaboration with the Svalbard Integrated Observing System (SIOS) community (e.g. webinars, publications, project clustering), providing useful spatial data for simple overlay analysis via our website (M8.1) and through project outputs (such as the BSAF). Open-access journal articles are less likely to reach this group, but results can be made more accessible via other products.

4.1.3 Members of the Scientific Community

Individuals, groups, or institutions who contribute to intergovernmental science-policy panels and platforms, such as IPBES, IPCC, international councils and bodies such as OSPAR, ICES Expert Groups, the Global Ocean Observing System, EU Polar Cluster projects, Arctic Council and associated working groups (PAME, CAFF), and other consortia.

In addition to these specific groups, early career researchers (ECRs), readers of scientific journals and the scientific journals themselves, such as ResearchGate or Elsevier, fall into this category, as well as other researchers working with related disciplines, in both natural and social sciences. Our secondary audience includes those conducting research in more applied settings such as engineering.

Objectives for the Scientific Community

Our objectives are to 1) inform large-scale, high-profile assessments, actively targeting workflows of groups like IPCC and IPBES and groups that work directly with ocean carbon, ocean observation, and/or polar and sub-polar systems, 2) give recommendations on future research priorities for ocean carbon, biodiversity and polar research through scientific publications and presentations, and open access data and models, 3) improve modelling efforts and approaches to better predict marine responses to climate change and resulting impacts to ecosystem services, and 4) leverage expert knowledge at conferences and in working or assessment group collaborations, as well as through joint EU Polar Cluster activities.

Channels and Outputs for the Scientific Community

Communication with this group is primarily through peer-reviewed, open access publication of scientific articles and uploading data to appropriate databases for future use (covered in the Data Management Plan). However, we also plan to engage the scientific community by featuring our consortium members and their research findings on our project website, promote the coverage of research articles in popular media and news outlets, and in social media and pioneering a mentorship program for ECRs wishing to become more actively engaged in promotion of their work outside of traditional publications.

4.1.4 European Civil Society and Arctic communities

Individuals, groups, or organizations who may be a part of NGOs, civil society organizations, citizen science initiatives, or involved in innovative sustainable industry that are impacted by melting sea ice and emerging novel ecosystems and who are motivated to make positive change. This target audience also includes school groups in Arctic communities and throughout Europe.

Objectives for European Civil Society and Arctic communities

Our objectives are to promote ocean literacy with a focus on Blue Carbon by highlighting Polar Blue Carbon habitats as a natural resource near them and to enhance public interest and understanding of Polar Blue Carbon, as it pertains to biodiversity and protection of the marine environment.

Channels and Outputs for European Civil Society and Arctic communities

Communication and messaging with this target group will ideally maximise two-way exchange of information, using tools such as podcast episodes and educational resources available on our project website, and multimedia events/exhibits.

4.2 Communication Strategies

This plan outlines generally how SEA-Quester will use clear and concise messaging, targeted, multi-channel communication to our primary audiences, consistent branding, and listening and responding to feedback to strategically communicate about the project throughout its 4-year lifecycle. General communications in the project operate under the general principles of “active and often” (both external audiences and internal partners), “nothing about us without us” for collaborations with Indigenous Peoples and/or local communities in the Arctic, and “KPI – Keep People Informed”.

A common undercurrent to all scientific research is that it is complex and research papers that describe it can be dense. Stripping away complexity for a more general audience puts communications at risk of becoming an oversimplified primer that does not really represent the latest findings (does not do justice to complexity), or conversely, communications that show the latest discoveries but lack proper context for people who are new to the topic (makes complexity a barrier).

To address this, GRID-Arendal is a proponent of the “clarify, not simplify” framework (proposed by Nigel Holmes in his book “Joyful Infographics”), where communications and dissemination outputs are seen as more translator or guide. The focus shifts from watering information down to knocking down barriers of entry and beckoning the reader or viewer in, with the goal of making specialized information accessible and instilling a sense of curiosity.

Some strategies for scientific communication under the “clarify don’t simplify” umbrella include embracing illustrations to organize complexity, using a clearly defined structure, including welcoming gestures, developing concrete analogies, reducing or eliminating jargon (visual, verbal, and written), leading with known points and following with uncertainty, avoiding assumptions (especially with multi-cultural audiences or highly politicized topics), and helping audiences make personal connections to the topic at hand.

4.2.1 Social Media

The project communicates with target audiences who are present on social media using Facebook and Instagram. The project utilises an Instagram audience previously gathered on a related EU Horizon Project – ECOTIP (Grant No. 869383) (approximately 300 followers) to cross-promote a joint SEA-Quester account. The project will use the ECOTIP Facebook account similarly. SEA-Quester does not maintain an account on X or LinkedIn but encourages SEA-Quester researchers to bring project results to their own audiences on those platforms. Any videos produced in association with the project can be launched on partner YouTube accounts.

SEA-Quester has an active but output-focused social media presence, with the goal of having each consortium partner contributing to 1 post per year (ideally featuring ECRs), with the remaining content curated from the EU Polar Cluster posts, re-posts from our sister project POMP, and other relevant events or news. To facilitate creating and managing this content, the project will develop and maintain a content calendar including promotion of events, fieldwork, and cruises. GRID-Arendal will assist project partners in producing batch content during field excursions and at annual General Assemblies to streamline posts and scheduling, as video content featuring researchers tends to receive the most engagement.

4.2.2 Media Outreach

The media strategy will focus on maximizing the exposure of the project in more mainstream media outlets. Recognising that the project has a limited lifetime, SEA-Quester will make good use of existing press offices and media relations through the partner institutions to maximise reach as well as offer financial support for journalists to join field expeditions and gain first-hand experience with polar research.

The media strategy is a high-exposure deliverable that has the most potential to reach less specialized audiences, and the impact of communicating the importance of Polar Blue Carbon, and the findings of the project to a much wider audience, cannot be overstated, depending on which media the stories, opinion editorials, and columns are published in. In these efforts, GRID-Arendal will use the following takeaways from the [Climate Explorer Project](#), in alignment with principles of [constructive journalism](#):

- Show science as a process, not a silver bullet.
- Remember that climate change is also about people – bring them into the conversation
- Cover international politics and policy by linking it with daily lives and showing the different voices of all countries involved
- Do not feed polarization by engaging with outrage and the extreme. Hold vested interests and politicians to account with facts.

Part of the media outreach strategy will be to establish a **media/press landing page** early in the project, which will be available on the SEA-Quester website, to enable media contacts to easily access the key project information and contacts for further coverage. The media package will be updated to contain the following:

- Short introduction to the project
- Links to latest results and press releases
- Key contacts (such as the SC members)

- Links to relevant website sections and project impacts, including testimonies from involved stakeholders and other polar cluster initiatives

GRID-Arendal will reach out to a variety of news outlets to keep them informed about SEA-Quester's work and published research. In addition to collaborating with institutions' press offices and targeting their networks of media contacts, GRID-Arendal will contact journalists at outlets identified in Section 5. These lists will grow and evolve as the SEA-Quester project progresses, and as partners share their contacts and recommendations.

4.3 Dissemination Strategies

SEA-Quester will ensure that project results are disseminated and exploited – commercially and in other research projects – as much as possible. Key to the success of the project's dissemination potential is the recognition of the following:

1. early identification of key stakeholders/target groups and establishment of contact / dialogue with them is essential to establishing a conducive environment to co-create meaningful knowledge and support quality engagement
2. identification and understanding of on-going or upcoming policy, scientific assessments, or other processes allows for sufficient time and planning to engage properly and strategically.

SEA-Quester will disseminate its results in scientific publications, conferences and databases, as well as through media outreach. Through targeted dissemination and exploitation activities, SEA-Quester will ensure uptake of project outcomes by the target stakeholders who need this information the most and who can influence policy and decisions on blue carbon. Dissemination activities carried out in the project will be tracked as part of routine reporting requirements.

4.3.1 Polar Clustering

Together with POMP and other Horizon-funded projects researching climate change impacts on polar ecosystems, carbon sinks, and biodiversity, with a special focus on the capacity of ecosystems to mitigate increasing atmospheric CO₂ concentration, SEA-Quester will coordinate to the extent that:

- We avoid overlap in key deliverables and outputs;
- We avoid conflicting results or key messages;
- We collaborate during policy outreach events and materials;
- We re-share social media content.

SEA-Quester and POMP project coordinators meet monthly to coordinate communication, dissemination and exploitation activities; additionally, POMP and SEA-Quester ECRs gather separately to plan for events or field work. Additionally, GRID-Arendal and Science Cruncher (communication leads for SEA-Quester and POMP respectively) are in email contact regularly for social media posts, collaborative fact sheets, attending events, and other joint activities, and POMP website updates are always shared in the SEA-Quester newsletter. Additionally, POMP and SEA-Quester will consider contributing comments for revisions to EU Policy and Legislation for the Arctic and Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD) jointly through the "Have Your Say" portal.

As of 2026, SEA-Quester has collaborated with the BioEcoOcean and NECCTON project on a jointly organized workshop on the topic of benthic carbon data products for advanced modelling, and

established collaboration with an ESA-funded project Phytodiverse which specifically targets ongoing EU projects to add value to their planned outputs.

SEA-Quester corresponds regularly with the EU Polar Board and is planning joint events in 2026. EUPB is organizing a session on impact and science communication during Arctic Science Summit Week, and SEA-Quester will cover the cost of a booth and apply for a plenary session at Arctic Circle Assembly for the benefit of all EU Polar Cluster projects, with the EUPB to help with project coordination and applications.

4.3.2 Dissemination Events

SEA-Quester will strategically use Arctic policy events to jointly disseminate results with sister or similarly themed projects on behalf of the EU Polar Cluster, to maximize impact and avoid stakeholder fatigue. A list of possible (recurring) events include:

- January – Arctic Frontiers
- March – Arctic Science Summit Week
- September – EU Polar Science Week
- October – Arctic Circle Assembly
- December – Arctic Futures Symposium
- Arctic Circle Forums
- International Conference on Arctic Research Planning ([ICARP](#))

Political events are also opportunities to communicate project activities and disseminate results, in the form of presentations, policy briefs, posters or exhibitions, and outreach/recommendations. Other events where there may not necessarily be EU Polar clustering, but which are still highly relevant for our project to actively participate include:

- June – UN Ocean Conference (every 3-4 years)
- November – Greenland Science Week (bi-annually)
- November – UNFCCC COP (annually)
- October – CBD COP (biannually)

4.4 Exploitation Strategies

The project's exploitation strategy relies on key products (deliverables, publications, datasets, flagship outputs) successfully communicated and disseminated to our target audiences. Whether or not these knowledge products are then used for marine spatial planning, governance, or informing future research efforts, is ultimately a reflection of communication and dissemination efforts; but exploitation is not merely a passive process.

Using knowledge transfer tools, such as those provided by the European Commission (e.g. Horizon Results Booster, see Section 5 below), and ongoing stakeholder engagement efforts, SEA-Quester will facilitate effective and meaningful application of project and expert knowledge to extract actionable insights, help make informed decisions, and maximize the value of data collected and stored through our data management plan and GeoNetwork facility. All other major project outputs will be available to the public through our dedicated community on the free and open Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/communities/sea-quester/>). The potential impact of the Zenodo community will

have increased after it was accepted as a sub-community of the EU Open Research Repository in mid-2025.

SEA-Quester will liaise with other Horizon-funded projects in the EU Polar Cluster to optimise synergies among projects and increase the efficiency of results exploitation, including exploiting other EU Polar Cluster project results. To this end, we will actively engage with the EU Polar Research community via the Catalyst platform (<https://polarcatalyst.eu/>) taking advantage of new initiatives akin to, for example, the CORDIS Results Pack on Polar Regions.

4.4.1 Exploitation of Data

Project results will be disseminated to stakeholder groups at a series of events, targeted policy dialogues and factsheets/briefs. Open access to project activities, key products, and outcomes will be secured via the project website (through making embed codes available, for example), the SEA-Quester Zenodo community, and through promotional materials such as flyers, graphics, blog articles, about the outputs to raise awareness and increase usage of these results.

We will also actively point towards project data and services during expert working group meetings, technical workshops and scientific conferences, which are important venues for generating new ideas and enabling new professional connections.

4.4.2 Exploitation of New Knowledge

Through active participation in working groups, task groups of the EU Polar Cluster, partnerships, key deliverables, and through the legacy of early career researchers, SEA-Quester will measure the exploitation of new knowledge produced and assess initial impact.

Some of the relevant metrics to monitor impact include:

- User engagement, usage frequency and user feedback: Did users enjoy the content? Was it relevant for their work? Did they gain new useful knowledge or develop new mindsets?
- Knowledge contribution – number of articles being published and cited
- Rating the discoverability of the data (through feedback)
- Adoption rate and data-driven decisions (NVivo Software)

4.4.3 Risks and barriers to exploitation and their mitigation

There are risks and barriers that could potentially influence the exploitation of SEA-Quester results (Table 1). SEA-Quester will assess and monitor these and update strategies to mitigate them.

Risk or barrier	Mitigation strategy
Deliverables necessary for following tasks are delivered late or incomplete: LOW	The project coordination office has a time plan for milestones and deliverables and will ensure these are delivered on time in accordance with the lump-sum grant agreement structure. It should be noted that payment does not occur unless deliverables are submitted and accepted, according to this structure.
Not enough time for dissemination and exploitation of project results at the end of the project: HIGH	A deadline for submitting deliverables earlier than the project end date would allow time for disseminating and utilising these within the project period.

Risk or barrier	Mitigation strategy
	OR Flagship outputs need to be planned early and not conflict with other deliverable dates.
The quality of deliverables is unsatisfying: LOW	Each deliverable will be circulated internally and peer-reviewed before being submitted, ensuring quality that is acceptable to all involved in the research. AND Through feedback and revisions, each partner has ongoing QA/QC processes
The conflict between policy process (NDCs, EU) timelines and project results: LOW	This is a real risk; however, the policy processes are usually known and can be planned for.
A lack of stakeholder interest, engagement or understanding for SEA-Quester work: HIGH	This is a real and serious risk (especially due to policymaker fatigue and time limitations from both project partners and decision makers), but our work is to ensure that what is communicated and disseminated is relevant to specific target groups, interesting, understandable and that we engage. AND Clustering with partner or sister projects to reduce fatigue while maximizing positive interactions and make the most effective recommendations.
The unplanned, extended absence of a work package lead: LOW	While this could happen, the project partners and grant agreement have processes to select a replacement in the event of extended leave.
Constraints due to events of nature or out of project control: LOW	Research on Polar areas is susceptible to seasonal weather conditions; however, these are known and can also be planned for during the cruise permitting process. AND Exploitation of prior EU project data can also fill in some gaps.
Derived deliverables or flagship products that depend on prior outputs lack necessary inputs to be achieved: LOW	Although flagship outputs are outlined in the proposal, they are not explicitly listed in deliverables and milestones. However, they are built on results that do have specified deadlines that must be adhered to for project partners to receive funding.

Table 1 Mitigation strategy for risks and barriers to exploitation of SEA-Quester results

5. DEC Tools

This section covers processes to communicate within the project (internal to project consortium members) and to communicate and disseminate externally towards main target audiences. We plan to leverage several tools and specific channels to accomplish both routine and more targeted communications, as outlined below.

5.1 Tools for internal communication

5.1.1 ECR Mentoring

GRID-Arendal will provide limited and targeted, one-to-one support to 2-3 early career scientists (e.g. PhD students, post doctorates, pre-tenure track) involved in or hired by the SEA-Quester project who wish to enhance their skills on communications and media outreach.

This targeted support will be purposely open-ended to maximize engagement from both ECRs and their target audience. Examples include publishing opinion editorials (op-eds), running a project social media account, creating a blog, starting a podcast, video production, or designing an infographic. Storylines can also be incorporated into ECR-produced products, if desired. Once candidates are identified, GRID-Arendal staff will conduct an initial scoping and brainstorming session to identify potential outputs/outlets and timelines.

In addition to the mentoring, ECRs involved in the project meet monthly to coordinate among themselves their inputs to the larger project group and activities.

5.1.2 Intranet

SEA-Quester has established an internal file sharing and communications platform on NextCloud, accessible only to project partners listed in the grant agreement through a personalized login. The NextCloud domain (<https://nc.sea-quester.eu/login>) will also be accessible from the main SEA-Quester website as a clickable icon, thereby providing an easy place of entry for the consortium. The Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences (IOPAN) has agreed to host and manage NextCloud services for the duration of the project.

NextCloud will be used for internal project communications tasks, including (but not limited to): file sharing or storage, document and manuscript shared editing, scheduling, discussion forums, and a shared calendar. Public project documents will be available on NextCloud until approved for publication in e.g. journals or the SEA-Quester website. Please reference deliverable 9.2 – Communication Platform and Procedures, for more specific details.

A copy of this communications plan, dissemination plan, data management plan, and other guidance documents (i.e. branding guide, logos, PowerPoint templates), will be kept on file and accessible for project partners. For more information about data storage policies/procedures, please reference deliverable 7.3 - SEA-Quester Data Management Plan.

5.1.3 Project Gatherings and Meetings

The Scientific Steering Committee, consisting of the Coordinator, Project Manager, and work package leads, will meet bi-annually, while the larger consortium with all partners involved will meet yearly at the General Assembly. Steering committee meetings will be held online using NextCloud or another appropriate platform, such as MS Teams or Zoom, except those in connection with the General Assembly, which are in-person events hosted by partner institutions on a rotating basis. These meetings are an opportunity for the outreach team to capture news of latest project research results and to co-create content for the communication channels, as well as set up a content calendar for the year.

In addition to steering committee meetings and general assemblies, task groups can be created by the coordinator as needed and composed of individuals across work packages. Examples include

permitting, planning, and arranging research cruises, and planning for attendance or participation at policy events. Work package leads are also expected to organize semi-regular meetings.

The project Advisory Board (established by the coordinator and project lead institution) will take part in one SSC meeting annually (preferably at the same time as a General Assembly) to give feedback and direction of the project. This is detailed further in D9.1

5.1.4 Nested Storylines

Storylines are a bridge between internal and external communications and outline key messages that will be co-developed during the initial project setup, modified and disseminated as results come in, and utilised after project end. Often described as an “elevator pitch”, storylines describe overarching concepts succinctly and can be tailored to the target audience.

Storylines can be turned into concrete outputs like infographics, webinars, fact sheets, videos, or longer blog-type posts. They can also be internal documents for project partners to use as a quick reference when speaking to the media or introducing new people or team members to the project.

An overarching storyline acts as an umbrella for the overall project narrative, while allowing for more specific storylines to be added later as needed. Sub-storylines or nested storylines focus on more specific topics or outputs and are often better appreciated once an audience member has the overall project context. For example, “trait-based modelling approaches” could be a sub-story within a larger “determining carbon sequestration time” storyline.

Internal Guidance for project partners regarding Storylines is provided in the Annex. At the 2025 SEA-Quester General Assembly, consortium partners agreed to focus on the following storylines: Biomass sequestration, Fate of primary production and Regime shifts and phenology.

5.1.5 “Mini-Guides”

To encourage consortium partners to actively engage in promoting SEA-Quester activities, we will have a ready-made communications toolkit containing commonly requested information/products or a step-by-step guide they need to promote their activities, such as presentation and poster templates, logos, branding guide, or social media post guidelines.

This will be achieved through small “mini-guides” - a single printable page, digital checklist, or short video tutorial with detailed instructions. Some examples are below, but topics will ultimately be based on consortium member needs and requests:

1. *Publication Checklist* (open access considerations, Zenodo, internal notifications)
2. *Presentation Checklist* (PowerPoint templates, how to display the logo, science communication principles, ask for the recording or possibility to record)
3. *Interview Checklist* (general interview advice, links to updated storylines, press release template)
4. *Metadata Sharing Checklist* (information on GeoNetwork, agreed metadata standards, support contact, link to wiki with common queries and solutions)

5.2 Tools for external communication and dissemination

External communication will mainly be in English, although other languages will be considered and prioritized when communicating with Arctic communities, particularly for the website.

5.2.1 Open Access Journal Articles and Scientific Databases

These products serve as the foundational outputs for the SEA-Quester project and are well suited to reach the Scientific Community. However, this communications plan will focus on creating more approachable products and messages based on these outputs that other audiences can also use.

5.2.2 Website

The project website acts as a hub for all target audiences, serving as the common jumping off point for project communications and an innovative flagship product (M7.1). This will take the form of an “animator-explainer” style website on polar blue carbon that will be updated throughout the project. This website has several domain names: polarbluecarbon.eu, seaquester.eu, or sea-quester.eu.

Three target audience groups (Scientific Community/ECRs, Local/National Governments, and International Policymakers) have specific pages with tailored products and information. Upper division undergraduate/graduate students, Blue Carbon professionals (affiliated with NGOs or financial sector), and other EU Polar Cluster Researchers may also visit the website and can engage with the animation to start exploring. Other audiences and engaged EU citizens, as well as our other target audiences, can choose to engage with the animation from the home page to learn more about Polar Blue Carbon. Since the project website is intended for external audiences, and to eliminate jargon, mentions of specific project work packages, tasks, or deliverables will be avoided. Emphasis will instead be placed on explaining and visualizing scientific concepts and providing policy-relevant tools and information, with links to additional resources.

The goals of the website are:

1. All audiences receive a foundational understanding of the concept of polar Blue Carbon (impart knowledge);
2. Provide an interactive, visual opportunity to learn more and dive deeper into project topics (instil curiosity/communicate nested storylines);
3. Understand the overall project and how individual project tasks fit into the larger picture;
4. Promoting project researchers and ECRs (showcase expert knowledge).
5. To disseminate the project’s results through interactive maps, factsheets, podcast episodes and other online learning tools through the website’s [Outreach page](#).

GRID-Arendal and IOPAN are responsible for the operation, maintenance, and upkeep of the project website. The website content will be managed/updated by GRID-Arendal but will be maintained by IOPAN who has agreed to host and manage the project website for the duration of the project and for at least 2 years after the project’s end date.

5.2.3 Newsletter

The project will communicate with target audiences as well as internal interested parties, such as the European Commission, via a [project newsletter](#) to be distributed by email to project members and stakeholders. The newsletter will also be available on the project website for anyone to view and will also be sent to the EU Polar Cluster for inclusion to their bi-annual newsletter.

SEA-Quester will maintain contact lists for both internal project partners, external guests, and collaborating partners associated with the project in accordance with the EU’s General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) guidelines. SEA-Quester will trial providing the latest newsletters directly on its website and promoted through, instead of having potential audiences “opt-in” to

receive email notifications. This functionality can easily be added to the website if needed at a later stage, however.

5.2.4 Promotional Materials

Promotional materials to be displayed and distributed at the major polar policy events where key target audiences will be present include materials such as flyers, posters, and a roll-up which display the project's logo, funding source and main themes and/or activities. Factsheets will also be developed as project results come in, including joint fact sheets with our sister project POMP.

5.2.5 Podcast Series

As another flagship communication product, GRID-Arendal will develop a podcast series, consisting of at least two "seasons" and bringing the actual voices of researchers and policy experts and the sounds of a polar research expedition to target audience groups who are interested in going more in-depth into certain topics. We will also explore partnerships with more popular and established science, policy, or news podcasts, which could help expand our audience.

The style of the podcast will be friendly, moderated discussions between two or more experts, or the host talking with one expert to tell a Polar Blue Carbon-related story. Each episode will aim to be 30-50 min. and can feature an expanded dive into a storyline, showcase a surprising result, or discuss implications or interesting questions. Examples of episode ideas include: discussing potential conflicts between managing marine environments ecosystem services like carbon sequestration and human activities, such as fishing or tourism, debating whether or not biodiversity policy can or should apply to the marine microbiome, or a short segment asking our researchers to respond about science in the news such as the recent discovery of "[dark oxygen](#)".

5.2.6 EU Commission Tools

- Horizon Results Booster: services for portfolio dissemination and exploitation Strategy; Business plan development and go-to-market support.
- Research and Innovation success stories: success stories from EU-funded R&I projects.
- CORDIS: articles and publications that highlight research results in an open repository
- Horizon Magazine: news about thought-provoking science and innovation projects
- Innovation Radar: including the recently launched Innovation Radar Bridge to strengthen connections between investors, innovators, and policymakers through targeted events, deep-dive thematic reports, and mobilising intelligence for market uptake
- Catalyst: forum for discussions with other polar researchers from around the world, notifications of the latest news, publication of own resources, calls, and events

5.3 Social Media

Each consortium partner will actively contribute to promoting their contributions to the project activities in social media by tagging the project, and/or also sending relevant information (pictures, links, text) to GRID-Arendal for upload to the relevant channels. Project hashtags are: #SEA-Quester, #polarbuecarbon or #SeqCSea. The content calendar for the project will be suggested collaboratively by consortium members at monthly meetings, with GRID-Arendal following up on these.

Partner institutions will be encouraged to use their existing social media channels to tag the project in posts about project-related activities. Materials for promotion can also or alternatively be sent to GRID-Arendal for posting via project social media channels. SEA-Quester and POMP will collaborate

on social media posts, particularly on joint efforts such as the joint webinar series from January until June 2026, where both SEA-Quester and POMP will promote across all channels and the recordings posted to the POMP YouTube channel and promoted via the Polar Cluster.

Blue Carbon & Biodiversity in the Arctic
A joint SEA-Quester and POMP webinar series

- **January 12, 2026 (15:00 CET)**
Speaker: Dorte Krause-Jensen (AU, Denmark)
Macroalgae and blue carbon in the Arctic.
- **February 9, 2026 (15:00 CET)**
Speaker: Christof Pearce (AU, Denmark)
Paleoceanography and long-term carbon burial in sediments.
- **March 9, 2026 (15:00 CET)**
Speaker: Bodil Bluhm (UiT, Norway)
Arctic benthos: its role for biodiversity and carbon cycling.
- **April 13, 2026 (15:00 CET)**
Speaker: Morten Iversen (AWI, Germany)
Recycling and flux attenuation in changing ecosystems.
- **May 11, 2026 (15:00 CET)**
Speaker: Mathieu Ardyna (Takuvik – ULarval, Canada)
Arctic primary production in a rapidly changing ice-covered ocean.
- **June 15, 2026 (15:00 CET)**
Speaker: Sigrun Huld Jonasdottir (DTU, Denmark)
Lipid-rich polar copepods: Life history strategy under climatic threat?

Funded by the European Union

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GRID-Arendal uses Hootsuite to manage social media posting and analytics, which has allowed us to exploit insights gained from the audiences acquired during ECOTIP project to better inform social media efforts for SEA-Quester. The data below suggests times (in Central European Time) when our followers are most active currently, so social media posts will be scheduled accordingly, and changes in user activity accounted for throughout the duration of the project.

Global celebration day posts will also be considered for the following themes: World Wildlife Day (03 March), International Day for Biological Diversity (22 May), World Environment Day (05 June), World Oceans Day (08 June), World Habitat Day (07 October), World Fisheries Day (21 November).

5.4 Media Outreach

GRID-Arendal and the press office of partner institutions will work together to reach out to the press: locally and internationally. Each consortium partner is responsible for alerting GRID-Arendal to activities that can be promoted and providing the relevant content.

6. Action Plan

The action plan outlines the plan of work with a timeline and clear responsibilities for the above-mentioned external communication tools and tasks, summarizing the basic questions of “Who? What? When? Where? And Why?” for easy reference. The table will be updated as roles within the project become more defined and outputs/deliverables are developed.

WHAT? The measure	WHO? target audience	WHEN?	WHERE?	HOW? Objective and message	BY WHOM? Responsible partner
Project gatherings / working group check-ins	Project consortium members, Steering Committee	Monthly, Yearly, as needed	Online and in-person	Progress updates and news or results to promote, upcoming plans	Project Coordinator Team (DTU), SC, WP Leads
ECR Mentorship	Early Career Researchers	Project Years 2+	Online and in-person		GRIDA
Intranet	Project consortium members	Entire project duration (4+ years)	NextCloud (online cloud services)	Internal coordination, manuscript editing, scheduling, planning	IOPAN
Storylines	All target audience groups	Entire project duration (4+ years)	DEC Plan, Intranet	FOCUSED Comms - discuss project with stakeholders through clear messaging	GRIDA develops, SC contributes, GRIDA to update
Website	All target audience groups	Entire project duration (4+ years) Quarterly narrative updates	www.polarbluecarbon.eu sea-quester.eu seaquester.eu	WordPress + SliderRevolution Plug-In; fill a critical information gap on Polar Blue Carbon, direct audiences to specific outputs	GRIDA develops and updates, IOPAN hosts domain names and maintains ALL partners responsible for contributing to featured content
Newsletter	EU Polar Cluster, European Commission	Quarterly	Website, Simple Visual Link via email	Microsoft Sway, general updates and news	GRIDA, Project Coordinator Team (DTU)
Social media channels					
Facebook	Scientific Community, Greenlandic Community	Monthly	ECOTIP + SEA-Quester Joint Account	External links to project outputs, promotion for events, profiling research team	ALL project partners to provide content, GRIDA to manage
Instagram	European civil society and Arctic communities	Monthly	ECOTIP + SEA-Quester Joint Account	External links to project outputs, promotion for	ALL project partners to provide content, GRIDA to manage

WHAT? The measure	WHO? target audience	WHEN?	WHERE?	HOW? Objective and message	BY WHOM? Responsible partner
				events, profiling research team	
Media outreach	Media outlets at local, regional and international levels	As needed or as project results come in	Primarily digital news outlets, podcasts, and potentially high-profile political events	News stories resulting from inviting journalists to join research cruises and fieldwork, Press Releases	GRIDA publishes press releases and contacts media AND Partners re-publish/promote within their networks
Press contact page	For all media inquiries or contacts, like a business card for our project	Entire project duration (4+ years)	On the project website, also available on GRIDA website	To give media easy access to all the information they need and to prompt more media interest	GRIDA
Promotion materials	For display and distribution at Polar events	Entire project duration (4+ years)	Stands or posters in high-traffic areas, videos on monitors, dependent on venue	Striking, eye-catching visuals to provide a conversation starter for project partners in attendance	GRID-Arendal produces, in collaboration with POMP, Project Consortium requests upon demand
Webinars	GRID-Arendal, POMP, and potentially cluster partners (SIOS)	Yearly, as needed/ requested	Zoom, WebX, <i>platform TBD</i>	Potentially relevant for as broad an audience as possible, prioritize platform with long-term links	GRID-Arendal or POMP to co-host, record, or livestream and post on YouTube

WHAT? The measure	WHO? target audience	WHEN?	WHERE?	HOW? Objective and message	BY WHOM? Responsible partner
Horizon Results Booster	Scientific Community, EU-level policymakers	Entire project duration (4+ years)	Online	Maximize project impact for strategic decision making, informed innovation, and operational efficiency	IOPAN, Project Coordinator Team (DUTU)
Podcast series	ECRs, students (high school – undergrad)	Q2, Year 1 to draft plan for first season	Remotely, with guidance from GRID-Arendal	Podcasts are a popular way to consume media and information – conversational tone helps inspire curiosity “a curated walk through a topic”	GRIDA to produce, featuring project partners and ECRs as guests
Multimedia exhibit	GRIDA, with contributions from all WPs	Second-half project (Years 2-4+)	Relevant Polar events and locations	Striking visuals with welcoming gestures, people on hand to answer questions and provide more info if needed	GRIDA to design and produce
Educational app called <i>Kangerluk</i>	Greenlandic youth and local communities	Second-half project (Years 2-4+)	App available for download for both Android and Apple devices	Increase blue carbon awareness and ocean literacy for Greenlandic citizens	GINR, with assistance from other partners as requested
Joint EU Polar Cluster activities	EU Civil Society, EU Citizens, EU Research Community	Relevant polar events where target audiences are present	See 4.3.2 for a list of events	Opportunities to communicate project activities and disseminate results to relevant target audiences in-person, and utilise findings	GRIDA, IOPAN, SC members

WHAT? The measure	WHO? target audience	WHEN?	WHERE?	HOW? Objective and message	BY WHOM? Responsible partner
				from all Polar Cluster projects	
Open-access journal articles	Scientific Community, (experts within natural or physical sciences and marine disciplines)	Within 6 months of data collection preferred	Open-access, peer-reviewed journals, available digitally	collecting novel data and new approaches + any technical limitations clearly stated, ensuring replicability under scientific method	ALL project partners, outreach to non-technical audiences by GRIDA
Data sets/products	Scientific Community, (experts within natural or physical sciences and marine disciplines), IPCC	As soon as results become available, including metadata	GeoNetwork + Zenodo + relevant large databases		ALL project partners, IOPAN to assist, manage, and monitor impact
Project reporting	EU Commission, Project Partners	Every 6 months	EC project portal (Funding and Tenders)	Written report outlining achievements and efforts to date	Project Coordinator Team (DTU), with financial info and updates from ALL partners
Policy briefings	National government reps/NDC decision makers, regional decision makers	Second-half project (Years 2-4+)	See 4.3.2 for a list of events AND Direct meetings, if possible	What is the relevant information from the project for use in strategic decision making? Clear,	Partner press offices, GRIDA, with support from Project Coordinator Team (DTU)

WHAT? The measure	WHO? target audience	WHEN?	WHERE?	HOW? Objective and message	BY WHOM? Responsible partner
	(RFMOs), international policymakers			actionable items based on data	
Conference sessions	National and International policymakers or decision makers, Scientific Community	Entire project duration (4+ years) or if invited	See 4.3.2 for a list of events	Partners to promote their work to specialized audiences in attendance	Consortium members' press offices and/or with support from GRID-Arendal

Table 2. Communication Action Plan

7. Inventories and Networks

7.1 Inventory of Relevant Projects, Organizations, and Associations

Based on overlapping project and research interests and mandates, below is a list (not exhaustive) of polar projects, consortiums, and international organizations relevant for SEA-Quester, as well as links to their websites (when available).

- *Ongoing (relevant) EU Horizon projects:*

Polar Ocean Mitigation Potential, [POMP](#), sister project, [PolarRes](#), [MPA Europe](#), [Arctic PASSION](#), [SO-CHIC](#), [OCEAN-ICU](#), [BIOcean5D](#) and [MARBEFES](#), [MARCO-BOLO](#) and [OBAMA-NEXT](#), [BLUE4ALL](#) and [OCEAN Citizen](#), [C-BLUES](#), [DTO-BioFlow](#) and DIGI4ECO, [CLIMAREST](#), and [BioEcoOcean](#), [NECCTON](#), [PLANT Project](#), [Phytodiverse](#).

- *Research consortiums, assessment groups, and polar scientific committees:*

[EU PolarNet2](#) and [Catalyst](#), [EU PolarCluster](#), [EU Polar Board](#), Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System ([SIOS](#)), Southern Ocean Observation System ([SOOS](#)), [ESA Carbon Science Cluster](#), [ESA Ocean Science Cluster](#), International Arctic Science Committee ([IASC](#)), All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance ([AAORIA](#)), Global Ocean Observing System ([GOOS](#)), Sustaining Arctic Observation Networks ([SAON](#)), International Ocean Colour Coordination Group ([IOCCG](#)), International Ocean Carbon Coordination Project ([IOCCP](#)), JPI Oceans [Blue Carbon Knowledge Hub](#), Integrated Marine Biosphere Research ([IMBeR](#)), Surface Ocean Lower Atmosphere Study ([SOLAS](#)), World Climate Research Program ([WCRP](#)), Arctic Spatial Data Infrastructure ([Arctic SDI](#))

- *Conventions and other international bodies:*

International Council for Exploration of the Sea ([ICES](#)), Oslo and Paris Conventions ([OSPAR](#)), Baltic Marine Environment Protection Commission ([HELCOM](#)), North-East Atlantic Fisheries Commission ([NEAFC](#)), Northwest Atlantic Fisheries Organization ([NAFO](#)), [The Arctic Council](#) and working groups for Protection of the Arctic Marine Environment ([PAME](#)) and Conservation of Arctic Flora and Fauna ([CAFF](#)), Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change ([IPCC](#)), Intergovernmental Science-Policy Platform on Biodiversity and Ecosystem Services ([IPBES](#)), International Maritime Organization (IMO), International Seabed Authority (ISA), [UN Decade of Ocean Science](#), Convention for Biological Diversity ([CBD](#)), UN Framework Convention on Climate Change ([UNFCCC](#)), [West Nordic Council](#), International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN) [Global Marine and Polar Programme](#), [Blue Carbon Initiative](#), UNEP/GEF [Blue Forests Project](#), World Resources Institute (WRI) [Oceans Program](#)

- *Environmental, climate, and fisheries ministries and agencies*

NORWAY: Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment ([KLD](#)), Norwegian Environmental Agency ([Miljødirektoratet](#)), Norwegian Institute for Nature Research ([NINA](#)), Norwegian Institute for Water and the Environment ([NIVA](#)), Norwegian Ministry of Trade, Industry, and Fisheries ([NFD](#)), Institute of Marine Research (IMR, [Havforskningsinstituttet](#)), Research Council of Norway ([Forskningsrådet](#)), [Nordic Council of Ministers, Governor of Svalbard](#)

GREENLAND: [Greenland Research Council](#), Fisheries Council ([Aalisarneq pillugu Siunnersuisogatigiit](#)), Department of Fishing and Catching ([Aalisarnermut Piniarnermullu Naalakkersuisoqarfik](#)), Fisheries Commission, Greenland Parliament ([Inatsisartut](#)), Greenland Government ([Naalakkersuisut](#))

ICELAND: Icelandic Centre for Research ([RANNIS](#)), [Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries](#), Iceland Institute of Natural History ([IINH](#)), [Ministry of the Environment, Energy, and Climate, Environmental Agency of Iceland](#)

DENMARK: Environmental Protection Agency ([Miljøstyrelsen](#)), Government of Greenland, [Ministry of Food, Agriculture, and Fisheries](#) of Denmark, Danish Fisheries Agency ([Fiskestyrelsen](#)), Danish Energy Department ([Energistyrelsen](#)), The Council on Climate Change ([Klimarådet](#))

7.3 Target Media Networks

GRID-Arendal completed a review of target media networks, based on overlap with target audiences, our in-house journalist network, prior experience, and overall reach/quality of work. Potential news outlets the project could collaborate with are listed below:

- *Science news outlets:*

[Science News](#), [Science News for Students](#), [New Scientist](#), Popular Science, Horizon Magazine, [ScienceDaily](#), Live Science, Undark, National Geographic, [United Academics Magazine](#), [Scientific American](#), [Science](#), [Sci News](#), [Phys Org](#), [The Conversation](#).

- *European general and environmental news outlets:*

The Economist, [The Guardian - Europe](#), [Politico EU](#), Climate Home News, Carbon Brief, ClimateNews Network, [BBC News Europe](#), [Euronews](#), [Aljazeera Europe news](#), [CNN Europe](#), [Reuters](#), [BBC Science & Environment](#), [Environmental News Network](#), [The Guardian - Environment](#), [PEER: Partnership for European Environmental Research](#)

- *Arctic general and environmental news outlets:*

Target publications could include [Arctic Today](#), [Eye on the Arctic](#), Arctic Portal News Portlet, [The Guardian - Arctic](#), [BBC News -Arctic](#), [Over the Circle](#), [eco environment coastal and offshore](#), [High North News - News, analysis and debate about politics and business in the North](#)

- *Regional Arctic news outlets:*

[Global news](#) (Canada), [Nunatsiag News](#) (Canada), [The Arctic Sounder](#) (Alaska), [Anchorage Daily News](#) (Alaska), [The Arctic](#) (Russian and English), [The Barents Observer](#) (Russia, Norway), [High North News \(Norway\)](#), [yle news](#) (Finland), [CBC News - Indigenous](#); The Arctic Today, APTN (Canada)

- *Arctic journalists:*

[Arctic bureau freelance journalist contacts](#)

- *Polar news:*

[Polarjournal | News aus den polaren Regionen](#),

7.4 Social Media Channels

GRID-Arendal completed an inventory of project consortium members and target audience organisations present on social media, the results of which are summarized in Table 3, outlining current accounts that are in use and could potentially be targeted or serve as curated content sources.

	Facebook	Instagram	LinkedIn	X	YouTube	Mastodon
TOTAL	23	18	14	26	20	3
Consortium members						
The Technical University of Denmark (DTU)	Danmarks Tekniske Universitet - DTU	@dtudk	DTU - Technical University of Denmark	@DTUtweet	@DTUbroadcast	
The University of Bremen		@uni_bremen	University of Bremen		@unibremen	@unibremen@wi sskomm.social
Pinngortitaleriffik / Greenland Institute of Natural Resources (GINR)	Pinngortitaleriffik, Grønlands Naturinstitut		Grønlands Naturinstitut			
AWI	Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research	@AWIexpedition		@AWI_Media	@AWIresearch	
The Leibniz Institute for Baltic Sea Research, Warnemünde (IOW)	IOW Leibniz-Institut für Ostseeforschung Warnemünde			@Ostseeforschung		
Åbo Akademi University (Åbo Akademi) #ÅAKÄRLEK	Åbo Akademi	@aboakademi	Åbo Akademi University	@AboAkademi	@aboakademi	

	Facebook	Instagram	LinkedIn	X	YouTube	Mastodon
Institute of Oceanology of Polish Academy of Sciences (IOPAN)	Instytut Oceanologii PAN		https://www.linkedin.com/company/iopan/		@instituteofceanologypan5519	
GRID-Arendal	GRID-Arendal	@gridarendal	GRID-Arendal	@GRIDArendal	@GridaNo	
Hereon	Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon	@hereon_helmholtz	Helmholtz-Zentrum Hereon	@HereonHelmholtz	@HelmholtzZentrumHereon	@hereon@helmholtz.social
Aarhus University (AU)	Aarhus Universitet	@aarhusuni	Aarhus University	@AarhusUni	@AarhusUniversity	
Imperial college, London (of Science, Technology and Medicine)	Imperial College London	@imperialcollege	Imperial College London	@imperialcollege	@imperialcollegevideo	
Brazilian National Institute for Space Research / Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas Espaciais (INPE)	Instituto Nacional de Pesquisas Espaciais	@inpe.oficial		@inpe_mcti	@inpeoficial	
Other EU Horizon Projects						
Sister Project POMP			POMP - Polar Ocean Mitigation Potential	@POMP_EU		

	Facebook	Instagram	LinkedIn	X	YouTube	Mastodon
Other Calls	Ocean Citizen Bioecocean		MARCO-BOLO	@MARCOBOLO_EU	@obama-next	
			OBAMA-NEXT	@ObamaNext	@oceancitizen_eu	
			BLUE4ALL	@oceancitizen_eu		
			OCEAN CITIZEN	@EO_OPEN_SCIENCE		
			BioEcoOcean	@BioEcoOcean		
				@PLANT_eu		

Target audiences on social media

Policymakers	Arctic Council	@europeanparliament	European Parliament	@Europarl_EN	@europeanparliament	#EUGreenDeal
	EUPolarNet			@eu_eeas		
	European Parliament	@eudiplomacy	European External Action Service	@ClaraGanslandt	@EUExternalAction	
	European External Action Service – EEAS	@ourplanet_eu	EU Environment and Climate	@EU_ENV	@EUEnvironment	
	EU Environment	@Eucouncil		@EUCouncil	@eucouncil	
	Council of the European Union	@europeancommission	Council of the European Union	@EU_Commission	@EU_Commission	
European Commission		European Commission				

	Facebook	Instagram	LinkedIn	X	YouTube	Mastodon
Scientific community	European Polar Board	@Allatlanticocean	European Polar Board	@EUPolarCluster	@EUPolarCluster	
		@oceancitizen_eu		@EuPolarBoard		
EU Polar Cluster		@ESA_EARTH	European Space Agency - ESA	@ArcticCouncil	@all-atlanticoceanresearch7716	
AllAtlanticOcean		@europeanspaceagency		@AllAtlanticO		
ESA - European Space Agency				@ESA_EO	@eopenscience4372	
				@esa	@EuropeanSpaceAgency	

Table 3. Social media accounts of consortium members

8. Impact Monitoring and Reporting

The “Who” (target audiences) and “What” (outputs and project activities) of the project has been identified in this deliverable and project proposal. The magnitude of project impact (“How Much”), relative contributions (“Our Roles”), and the risk to achieving these impacts are briefly discussed here. SEA-Quester will work to effectively measure, assess, and monitor project contributions to sustainable ocean governance, increased ocean literacy in the EU, and fact-based marine policies, in addition to producing discoverable, useable, and high-quality scientific advances.

Strategies for effective reporting include setting SMART goals (specific, measurable, achievable, realistic, and timely), budgeting time and resources to elicit specific feedback from target audiences, leveraging technology and tools to help monitor digital footprint, setting quantitative targets for formal reporting, setting qualitative targets for internal communication, and keeping project partners (especially the SEA-Quester Steering Committee and Advisory Board) informed in a timely manner.

Metrics, tools, and roles/responsibilities are addressed in Table 4 below. While project impacts to policy and decision making are harder to quantify, SEA-Quester outputs such as the policy assessment can help inform other flagship products and tool design later in the process and serve as an important baseline for follow-up and clarification.

Key Performance Indicators	Specific Metrics	Roles/Responsibilities
KPI1: Digital Communications	Website Analytics: Number of website unique visitors/unique visits/page views in reporting period, bounce rate, time spent engaged with animation, number of internal links used <i>Suggested Tool: Microsoft Clarity</i>	GRIDA, partners to provide beta testing feedback and relay testimonials from user groups
	Audiences: Number of attendees, survey results and feedback from questionnaire, number of questions received, likert scale ratings <i>Suggested Tool: SurveyKing</i>	All partners, GRIDA will collate
	Media Footprint: Total reach, articles mentioning or featuring the project, media coverage <i>Suggested Tool: InfoMedia</i>	GRIDA, with updates from all partners
	Newsletter Reach: Number of people viewing online newsletter <i>Tool: Microsoft Sway (provided automatically)</i>	GRIDA
	Social Media Engagement: Quantitative indicators such as the number of clicks, likes, shares, tags, video views, new followers, profile visits, engagement rate, use of #SEA-Quester hashtag and influence of the accounts that use it; Qualitative indicators such as types + tone of comments received, number of people reached, types of followers,	GRIDA

Key Performance Indicators	Specific Metrics	Roles/Responsibilities
KPI 2: Face-to-face meetings	<p>impressions, traffic data, ratings, word clouds etc. <i>Suggested Tool: Hootsuite</i></p> <p>Podcast Metrics: number of downloads vs streams, followers, listener countries, listener demographics, downloads over time, top episodes, social shares, audience reviews, website links from podcast (<i>monitoring tool TBD</i>)</p> <p>Audience: The number of people attending or participating in events including presentations, public lectures, seminars, etc. survey feedback, likert scale ratings <i>Suggested Tool: SurveyKing</i></p> <p>Events: Partner attendance at key polar policy events; presence of exhibition at key polar event; flyers/fact sheets at key polar events, invitations to participate in events; type, size, target audience of events <i>Suggested Tools: Event Recordings, Registration and Attendance</i></p> <p>Testimonials: number of requests for more information, number of new contacts; positive feedback from target audience members</p>	<p>All partners responsible for gathering estimates of the number of people attending events (in person or online)—will be collated by GRIDA</p> <p>Work Package 7</p>
KPI 3: Policy Uptake	<p>Quantitative Analysis: Number of messages delivered vs. baseline policy assessment before vs. after the project completion (international, regional, and national levels) <i>Suggested Tools: Nvivo Analysis</i></p>	<p>GRIDA, with input from partners and stakeholders</p>
KPI 4: Collaboration and synergies	<p>Polar Clustering: Number of partners engaged in activities led by or co-organised by SEA-Quester; number of activities sponsored/co-organised</p> <p>SoMe Clustering: SEA-Quester featured in other project/polar cluster social media, newsletters, or similar; number of posts from polar cluster projects on SEA-Quester's account <i>Suggested Tools: Hootsuite, Brand Mentions</i></p>	<p>All partners to encourage and report clustering activities; GRIDA to monitor social media</p>
KPI 5: Scientific Merit	<p>Horizon Results Booster: Reporting and metrics available from EU tools <i>Tool: EU Results Booster</i></p> <p>Data Usage: data uploaded vs downloaded, unique entries in GeoNetwork or similar database, data collection in new areas, contribution to ongoing long time series <i>Tools: GeoNetwork, Zenodo</i></p> <p>Scientific Publications: # of open access articles published, number of other scientific publications (policy</p>	<p>IOPAN</p> <p>IOPAN</p> <p>Input from all project partners required, IOPAN to collate</p>

Key Performance Indicators	Specific Metrics	Roles/Responsibilities
	directions, reviews, practitioner’s perspectives, and forum articles challenging existing work), average impact factor, number of citations Project Representation: Inclusion of project data or data products/studies/analysis in synthesis reports, GOOS, IASC, AAORIA, and ESA outputs	IOPAN

Table 4. SEA-Quester Key Impact Indicators and responsibilities for monitoring them

9. Annex – Practical guides

SEA-Quester’s contact/ mailing list, impact survey QR code, branding guide and storyline guidance.

Partners		e-mail		WP Lead	
P1	DTU	Marja Koski	mak@aqu.aqua.dtu.dk	Project lead	WP 9-11
	DTU	Sigrun Jonasdottir	sjo@aqu.aqua.dtu.dk	Project leader team	WP 9-11
	DTU	Andre Visser	awv@aqu.aqua.dtu.dk	Project leader team	WP 4 & 5
	DTU	Ole Henrik Haslund	ohha@aqu.aqua.dtu.dk	DTU Aqua project office	WP 9-11
	DTU	Dina Berenstein	dibe@aqu.aqua.dtu.dk	DTU Aqua project office	WP 9-11
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	DTU	Rafael Goncalves-Araujo	rafgo@aqu.aqua.dtu.dk		
P2	UBREMEN	Kai Bischof	kbischof@uni-bremen.de	PI, WP1 (co-)lead	WP1
	UBREMEN	Andrea Gottlieb	eu@vw.uni-bremen.de	EU office, admin tasks	
	UBREMEN	Sarina Niedzwiedz	sarina@uni-bremen.de	SeaQuester PostDoc	
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	GINR	Lorenz Meire	LoMe@natur.gl		
P4	AWI	Morten Iversen	Morten.Iversen@awi.de	WP Lead	WP 2
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	AWI	Maren Staniek	maren.staniek@awi.de	PhD (external fund)	WP 2
	AWI	Giulia Röeg	grueegg@mpi-bremen.de	PhD (partial fund)	WP 2
P5	IOW	Jörg Dutz	joerg.dutz@io-warnemuende.de		
	IOW	Maren Voss	maren.voss@io-warnemuende.de		
P6	ABO	Anna Törnroos-Remes	Anna.M.Tornroos@abo.fi		
	ABO	Christian Pansch-Hattich	christian.panshhattich@abo.fi		
	ABO	Christoffer Boström	christoffer.bostrom@abo.fi		
	ABO	Phoebe Armitage	phoebe.armitage@abo.fi		
	ABO	Gundel Westerholm	gundel.westerholm@abo.fi		
	ABO	Anna Lyubavina	anna.lyubavina@abo.fi		
	ABO	Kati Kemppainen	kati.kemppainen@abo.fi		
P7	IOPAN	Piotr Kowalczyk	piotr@iopan.pl	WP1 Co-Lead	WP1
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	IOPAN	Mirosław Darecki	darecki@iopan.pl		

	IOPAN	Joanna Stoń-Egiert	aston@iopan.pl		
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P8	GRIDA	Paige Hellbaum Eikeland	paige.eikeland@grida.no	Main Contact; WP Lead	WP 7-8
	GRIDA	Tina Schoolmeester	tina.schoolmeester@grida.no	GRID project team leader	WP 7-8
	GRIDA	Sabrina Heerema	sabrina.heerema@grida.no	Comms Lead	WP 7-8
	GRIDA	Steven Lutz	Steven.lutz@grida.no	Policy Assessment Lead	WP 7-8
	GRIDA	Olivia Rempel	Olivia.rempel@grida.no	Media Lead	WP 7-8
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	HEREON	Bryce Van Dam	bryce.dam@hereon.de		
	HEREON	Claudia Schmidt	claudia.schmidt@hereon.de		
P10	AU	Marit-Solveig Seidenkrantz	mss@geo.au.dk	Main Contact; WP Lead	WP4+5
	AU	Christof Pearce	christof.pearce@geo.au.dk		WP4+5
	AU	Rachel Lupien	rachel.lupien@geo.au.dk		WP4+5
	AU	Hamed Sanei	sanei@geo.au.dk		WP4+5
	AU	Henrieka Detlef	henrieka.detlef@geo.au.dk		WP4+5
	AU	Mads Ramsgaard Stoltenberg	mrs@geo.au.dk		WP4+5
P11	INPE	Emma L Cavan	e.cavan@imperial.ac.uk		

Thank you!

Tell us what you think – scan the QR code to take a quick survey.

www.seaquester.eu
www.polarbluecarbon.eu

BRANDING MANUAL

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101136480 (SEA-Quester)

CONTENTS

Vertical logo 5

Horizonatal logo

Exclusion zone 6

Misuse of logo

Partners logos 7

8

COLORS

Primary Colors 9

Secondary Colors

10

TYPOGRAPHY

Brand Typeface 11

Welcome

Consistent expression of the SEA - Quester brand is being achieved by the usage of these guidelines. The guidelines define what makes the SEA-Quester brand and explain how to create the look and feel of SEA-Quester's identity.

Disclaimer

*SEA-Quester is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or **[name of the other granting authority]**. Neither the European Union nor **the granting authority** can be held responsible for them.*

LOGO

Verticle Logo

This is SEA-Quester's primary logo format

Full color

Black

White

Horizontal Logo

This is SEA - Quester's secondary logo format

Full color

Best used on white background. Avoid using it with colored backgrounds.

Black

Works best on white background. Can also be used on a light-colored background.

White

Works best on black background. Can also be used on a dark-colored background.

Minimum Exclusion Zone

The recommended exclusion zone around the logo is shown here. The minimum clear space is equal to the thickness of the blue C in the logo.

Type, graphics, and other logos should never encroach on this minimum exclusion zone.

Misuse of Logo

Always use the master logo files. It is important that the logo is never altered.

Do not place type or graphics inside the exclusion zone.

Do not change the color of the logo to a color that's not specified in this manual.

Do not separate the different logo elements. Do

not stretch the logo or add perspective. Do not

tint the logo.

Do not add any effects to the logo, i.e drop shadows, et.c.

Funders and Partners Logos

The logos of the partners and funders should be included in a similar color format as SEA-Quester logo.

For instance, if the white SEA-Quester logo is used on a dark background, all partner logo should be used in a similar way. Same applies to black logo on a light background.

On the other hand, if the colored SEA-Quester logo is used on a light background, all partners and funders colored logo can be used.

European Flag and Funding Statement

All SEA-Quester communication activities related to the action for which the project received funding must acknowledge EU support and display the European flag emblem and the following funding statement:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101136480 (SEA-Quester)

Communication activities include all websites, media relations, conferences, seminars, information material such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.

Furthermore, any communication or dissemination activity that the project undertakes must contain the following disclaimer:

*SEA-Quester is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or **[name of the other granting authority]**. Neither the European Union nor **the granting authority** can be held responsible for them.*

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COLORS

Primary Colors

The use of these colors in the communication helps build brand awareness among SEA-Quester's target audience.

The colors that have specified percentage may be used as solid colors (100%) or in the permitted tint values shown here (20%, 40%, 60% 80%). Using tints helps extend the color palette for illustrations and information graphics that needs visual differentiation.

Green #09844c

Blue #4db8e2

Beige #e0bc82

Secondary Colors

The secondary color palette is developed to be used sparingly to complement the primary colors.

Violet #ba5af2

Orange #ed9945

Turquoise #66fff0

The image features a series of concentric, overlapping circles in various shades of blue, creating a layered, tunnel-like effect. The circles are centered on the page. In the center of the innermost circle, the word "TYPE" is written in a bold, white, sans-serif font. The overall composition is clean and modern, with a strong emphasis on geometric shapes and color contrast.

TYPE

Primary Typeface

SEA-Quester's main typeface is Adelle Sans.

In general, Light and Regular should be used in body copy. Medium and Bold should be used to highlight key information or provided emphasis, when needed.

Aa

Adelle Sans
Light

A B C D E F G H I J K

L M N O P Q R S T U V

W X Y Z Æ Ø Å

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Aa

Adelle Sans
Regular

A B C D E F G H I J K

L M N O P Q R S T U V

W X Y Z Æ Ø Å

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Aa

Adelle Sans
Semi Bold

A B C D E F G H I J K

L M N O P Q R S T U V

W X Y Z Æ Ø Å

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Aa

Adelle Sans
Bold

A B C D E F G H I J K

L M N O P Q R S T U V

W X Y Z Æ Ø Å

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Alternative Typeface

When using Microsoft Office Suite, we revert to our system typeface, Open Sans.

Aa

Open Sans
Regular

A B C D E F G H I J

K L M N O P Q R S T

U V W X Y Z Æ Ø Å

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

Aa

Open Sans
Bold

A B C D E F G H I J

K L M N O P Q R S T

U V W X Y Z Æ Ø Å

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9

SEA-Quester Project Storylines: A Nested Approach

What is a Storyline?

Think of a storyline as part of a conversation – someone at a conference asks what you are working on, and you think “SEA-Quester”! But what do you tell them?

Storylines are short, written versions of the verbal snippets or “elevator pitches” we use all the time to tell people about our project. If we write them down, we all have the same “story” to tell, and our messages become clearer and more concise.

Just as people will ask different questions based on what they are interested in; you can switch to different storylines within the project (“sub-storylines”) based on what they want to know.

In this way, different tasks and outputs of the project all fit together under one umbrella, but we can highlight different aspects of the project tailored to our audience – even if that is not our area of expertise.

A real-world example from the Ecosystem-based Management Conference in Tromsø:

What projects have you been working on lately?

The SEA-Quester project is looking at the phenomenon of polar blue carbon – how marine carbon sequestration will be impacted by the emergence of totally novel ecosystems due to climate change. Currently, we lack the ability to predict even the direction of change (positive or negative), so we hope to address this important data gap.

How will you look at interactions between new biological communities and changing physical conditions like ocean acidification or decreased oxygen?

We are utilizing new trait-based models to try to account for these complex interactions, and we are bringing together partners with different expertise (physical vs biological).

What do Storylines achieve?

- 1) Improved research focus
 - Storylines identify key questions from the stakeholder perspective (including assessment groups, policy makers etc.) and focusing SEA-Quester research towards answering these questions
- 2) Improved internal project communication
 - Storylines help to identify the links between WPs and tasks
 - Storylines clarify the concepts (systems) before starting the field campaigns which will help optimize sampling
- 3) Improved communication with external stakeholders
 - Storylines can be used to demonstrate SEA-Quester concepts / activities in connection to stakeholder events

- Storylines promote and clarify relevance for the media, in connection to other Arctic activities and events
 - Storylines can be “filled in” later for policy briefs, events, or exhibitions
 - Storylines can be updated as results come in - this makes writing fact sheets and producing other products much easier at later stages of the project!
- 4) Improved project exploitation
- Outputs that relate to specific research questions help others understand how SEA-Quester project results apply to new initiatives

What are the outputs?

- GRID-Arendal has produced an **overarching “umbrella” storyline for the project** animated for the SEA-Quester website (public)
- GRID-Arendal will also try to visualize how the remaining storylines fit into this larger narrative, through a **simple conceptual diagram to show the nested structure** (Prezi, MindMap, internal) **available for quick reference**
- We want to help produce **sub-storylines** (see below for ideas during the kick-off meeting) to be further developed in podcasts, exhibits, factsheets et cetera

To accomplish this, each WP should...

- Plan to **engage early career researchers**, with help and supervision from GRIDA (part of the mentorship program)
- **Review the list of storyline ideas** identified during the kick-off meeting OR
- **Write a list of innovative research questions** – what is really the front line of research related to the topic (new method, new area, new question, new approach..)
- Work with GRIDA to draft a **short description (700-800 words)** including broader relevance to society, science, or policy implications
- **Produce a conceptual figure / diagram / slide** to help illustrate the storyline(s)

Potential Storylines identified during the Kick-Off Meeting

- 1) Mass-balance perspective and steady-state
- 2) Marine organic carbon atlas
- 3) From Historical Reconstruction to Observations to Trait-based models
 - a) diatom-dinoflagellate ratio – what is it and why it is important?
 - b) How we use/measure/think about this ratio from the past (in sediments), the present (sampling on the cruise across different environments), and in the future (NUM models/trait-based modelling approaches)
- 4) Regime shifts and consequences – ecological tipping points & the carbon cycle
 - a) Benthic-Pelagic Coupling (*potential output – factsheet*)
- 5) Consequences of phenology shifts for the carbon cycle
 - a) Lipid Pump Shifts (*potential output – factsheets*)

- 6) Arctic Kelp – Biodiversity & Climate Change Interactions in the Arctic
- 7) What is the Fate of Primary Production?
 - a) Where primary production happens and how we measure it
 - b) Tracking the fate of a sinking particle – microbial and zooplankton processes that affect the path on the way to the seafloor.
 - c) When does sequestration happen?
- 8) Challenges of Monitoring Primary Production Remotely in the Arctic
- 9) Transport Modeling Matrix
 - a) how long does carbon stay in the ocean? Where does it come back up again?
- 10) Visualizing a Marine Sediment Core - time perspective
 - a) where do sediments come from? how much carbon is buried?
- 11) Trade-offs between ecosystem services
 - a) removing biomass and sequestration potential, and conservation vs value of use (sustainable or otherwise)
- 12) Biodiversity and implications for climate resilience/adaptation in an Arctic context
- 13) Main Storylines for Each Cruise (*output – internal use only*)
- 14) Coastal people, link local community solutions and global implications
 - a) teleconnections, ocean oscillations, microplastic or co2 export,
- 15) What do Emerging Communities mean for the Arctic food web?

WINNER & LOSERS

→ SYSTEM
→ GEOGRAPHICALLY

FATE OF CARBON
INORGANIC VS ORGANIC

EXPANDING

VS

SHRINKING

TIME?
SCALE
RESIDENCE
TIME
↳ MIL
↳ SPACED
↳ CAPTURE
↳ WATER

LATERAL
VS
VERTICAL
MECHANISM

UNDER ICE
WHAT IS HAPPENING THERE?
• DICE FRONT
• MOVEMENT
• TOOKER

VINOGRAPHY
LADDER
BP-COUPLING

SEA ICE AS A HABITAT
• LOSS OF SEA ICE IS NEGATIVE

STORYLINES FOR
CRUISES
(INTERNAL USE)

↑ N shift

ARXAR
VS
SUBSTRATE

SEA LEVEL RISE

• COMPLEXITY OF INVESTIGATING
THE MECHANISMS

• WHAT CAN I DO ABOUT THIS?
↳ link to local solutions
↳ can we provide off on the
helix?

